

COMPARATIVE INSIGHTS INTO ENGLISH LANGUAGE CURRICULUM DESIGN, PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICES, AND LEARNING OUTCOMES: A STUDY OF SSC AND GCE O-LEVEL SCHOOLS IN QUETTA

Aisha Alvi^{*1}, Ajaz Shaheen², Rafiq Ahmed³

^{*1}M. Phil Scholar, Faculty of Education, Lasbela University of Agriculture, Water and Marine Sciences, Uthal, Balochistan, Pakistan

²HoD of Education Department, Lasbela University of Agriculture, Water and Marine Sciences, Uthal, Balochistan, Pakistan

³Lecturer, Education Department. Lasbela University of Agriculture, Water and Marine Sciences, Uthal, Balochistan, Pakistan. Phd Scholer, SMIU

¹aishaalviluawms@gmail.com, ²dr.ajaz@luawms.edu.pk, ³rafiq.edu@luawms.edu.pk,

Corresponding Author: *

Aisha Alvi

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15354918>

Received	Revised	Accepted	Published
11 March, 2025	11 April, 2025	26 April, 2025	02 May, 2025

ABSTRACT

English has increasingly emerged as a vital language for academic advancement and access to higher education. This study focused on comparing the O-level and SSC English language curricula to identify the strengths and weaknesses in their aims and objectives and assessment patterns, recognizing that the school system serves as a gateway to higher education. The study reveals that while a large proportion of the population is satisfied with the English curriculum at the O-level, a majority of respondents are dissatisfied with the current SSC English curriculum. The English language proficiency of students at Senior Secondary School in Quetta is not up to the required level, largely due to outdated curricula that emphasize memorization rather than practical language use. Furthermore, the study critically examined and compared the pattern of assessment in both systems, specifically focusing on the content, practice, and design of examination papers. It was found that the SSC system's assessment pattern suffers from issues such as unintelligible content and a flawed exam paper design, which together fail to assess real language skills effectively. Assessment methods in the SSC system favor written examinations, neglecting the assessment of communicative competence. The study population consisted of 200 teachers (150 from the SSC system and 50 from the O-level system), 300 students (250 from the SSC system and 50 from the O-level system), and 40 English language experts (20 from each system) across 60 institutions. A mixed-method research approach was used, including both inferential and descriptive statistics, with the Chi-square test applied for comparison between the two education systems. Research instruments included three questionnaires for experts, teachers, and students, along with a semi-structured interview protocol and focus group discussions.

Keywords: English Language Curriculum; SSC (Secondary School Certificate); GCE (O-Level); Curriculum Objectives; Assessment Patterns; Exam Paper Design; Educational Systems in Pakistan; Quetta Schools.

INTRODUCTION

Since the establishment of Pakistan, English has been taught as a compulsory subject at all levels of education, from kindergarten to university. Today, English is the official language of Pakistan in the

fields of science, technology, law, government and education. It is also used as a second language. It is necessary and desirable for students to learn the fundamental rules and structures to read and

write good English (Akram & Mehmood, 2007). In Pakistan, there are two concurrent secondary education systems. Each system has its own curriculum, teaching strategies, facilities, equipment and assessment methods. "Matriculation" and "Intermediate" signifies the two phases of the first concurrent line, which follows the national curriculum and terminates with the Secondary School Certificate (SSC) and Higher Secondary School Certificate (HSSC) exam.

In this context, SSC and HSSC are the native educational system. SSC examinations are administered by two boards (local / federal). There are differences between the evaluation systems of Secondary/ local and Federal secondary education boards. Ordinary Level (O-Level) and Advanced Level (A-Level) are the GCE system's replacement for SSC and HSSC levels, respectively (Umbreen, 2018). Since 1959 the GCE programme has been operational in Pakistan. GCE (O-Level) is offered by a variety of institutions these days. GCE (O-Level) assessments are conducted by Cambridge Global Assessment (CIE) and Edexcel Worldwide London Assessment.

In Pakistan, the GCE (O-Level) and SSC run concurrently. It is generally recognized that the GCE English program, curriculum, teaching methods and assessment are significantly better than the SSC English program. O-level certificates are not offered to students in the public sector. O-level is exclusively taught in private schools. As a result, these two systems create an obvious divide amongst pupils. Particularly, Balochistan is the largest province of Pakistan. Despite being the richest province with abundant natural resources, Balochistan has long faced a number of problems in which poor education system is the prominent one. Baloch et al. (2022) noted that academic factors such as the syllabus, curriculum, and method of instruction have an effect on both the the potential of educational institutions and the conduct of students. The main goals of a successful educational system are accomplished through the curriculum. The curriculum serves as the cornerstone on which educational experiences and activities are created. In line with Kearsley and Lynch's(1996) assertions: the syllabus, which lists the course's aims and objectives, prerequisites, grading and evaluation policy, materials to be used (textbooks, software), topics to be covered, a

schedule, and a bibliography, is the most important aspect of a course's organization. The type of instruction is determined by each of these elements. While limiting the student's understanding base, targets and goals define the intended outcomes and course scope as determined by the teacher or course designer. Thus, as a legitimate continuation of the curriculum, the syllabus reflects all the academic material covered in a particular course. The syllabus emphasizes "accuracy and fluency, as well as form and function," with the goal of "making student's independent, capable of lifelong learning, creative thinking, problem solving and effective communication in English through aims and objectives set within the syllabus. However, no significant research had been conducted on the relative effectiveness of GCE (O- Level) and SSC English language curricula in Balochistan. Under these circumstances, a scientific study of the SSC and GCE (O-Level) systems was urgently needed to identify the advantages and disadvantages of English language curricula, syllabus and assessment systems in both educational system.

1.1 Research Objectives

- 1- To compare and analyze the aims and objectives in syllabus of English language at GCE (O- Level) and SSC system
- 2- To examine critically and compare the pattern of assessment for English language at GCE (O- Level) and SSC system by analyzing exam paper.

1.2 Research Questions

- 1- What are the flaws in the current SSC English language syllabus in terms of aims and objectives?
- 2- In the O-Level and SSC systems, what are the assessment patterns?

1.3 Research Hypotheses

- H1: The aims and objectives in syllabus of English language of GCE (O-Level) and SSC system are not significantly different from one another.
- H2: The assessment patterns of English language at GCE (O-Level) and SSC system is not significantly different from one another.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A review of the literature highlights significant

contrasts between the aims, objectives, and assessment patterns of English language education in the SSC and GCE (O-Level) systems. The National Curriculum for English language in Pakistan emphasizes a communicative approach, aiming to enable students to communicate accurately, appropriately, and fluently in real-life situations (Government of Pakistan, Ministry of Education Curriculum Wing, 2006). However, this goal is undermined by traditional teaching practices in public schools, which do not effectively develop students' communicative skills due to outdated syllabi, examination patterns, and teaching methodologies (Shamim, 2008). Moreover, English has been traditionally taught as a subject rather than as a language (Mahboob, 2009),

Hasan et al. (2005) conducts a linguistic study on the English language curriculum at the secondary level in Bangladesh. He discovers 82% of rural and urban secondary school students complain that English is not sufficiently used in the class. 68% teachers admit that they do not arrange the practice of the four skills (reading, writing, listening and speaking) of English language in the classroom. Conversely, the O-Level syllabus employs a learner-centered approach, addressing all four language skills—reading, writing, listening, and speaking (Cambridge O-Level English Language Syllabus 1123). Its aims include preparing students for real-life communication, practical use of English, and building a foundation for further study or employment (Cambridge Assessment International Education, 2021). Regarding assessment, according to Brown et al. (2002), it plays a vital role in shaping both teaching and learning processes. SSC assessments tend to emphasize rote memorization over analytical or critical thinking abilities (Ahmed & Shah, 2014). Questions largely originate from textbooks, promoting reliance on guess papers and guides that stifle creativity (Shamim, 2008). In contrast, O-Level assessments are designed to evaluate various language skills through directed writing, continuous writing, and comprehension tasks (Cambridge Assessment International Education, 2021).

These assessments prioritize real-life communication over memorization (Fareed et al. 2016) and aim to foster independent thinking (Cambridge Assessment International Education, 2021). Muhammad Iqbal Naem (2011) studied

and compares the SSC and GCE-O level English language courses to identify faults and inadequacies in the curriculum goals, instructional methods, content, and assessment system. The study determined that the SSC and O-level English language course goals were well-defined, unambiguous, and relevant to students' needs. In the O-level, they reached worldwide norms, but not in the SSC. The SSC examination system promoted cramming and rote memorization, but the O-level examination system promoted conceptual comprehension and hence creativity. In addition to integrating four abilities (hearing, reading, writing, and speaking), using technology and include current subjects like human rights and the environment in the curriculum were major proposals. Malik and Muhammad (2011) compared the teaching methods and evaluation practices in English subject at secondary school certificate (SSC) and general certificate of education GCE O-level in Pakistan.

The examination system also promotes understanding conceptual clarity instead of cramming. Malik and Anwar (2011) compared teaching techniques and assessment processes in English at SSC and GCE-O levels in Pakistan, the study explored that the exam approach also encourages intellectual clarity rather than cramming. According to Kiyani (2002), the main goals of the study were to compare the policy goals, study plans, curricular goals, subject matter, instructional strategies, and evaluation systems of the Pakistani SSC level with the British GCE-O level programme. Through this study, the researcher investigated that the GCE-O level curriculum creation process, curriculum objectives, curriculum contents, teaching techniques, and examination system in Pakistan were superior to those of the Secondary School Certificate (SSC). Bhatti et al., (2017) presented research focuses on comparative study of the Secondary School Certificate (SSC) and the General Certificate of Education-Ordinary level (GCE-O level) English language course to trace out the problems and shortcomings of the curriculum objectives and teaching methods. The main recommendations were that the SSC curriculum needs to be revised and modified according to the students' needs.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study compares English language teaching

effectiveness in Quetta's GCE (O-Level) and SSC systems, focusing on syllabus objectives and assessment patterns. It uses a mixed-method, descriptive approach involving questionnaires, semi-structured interviews, and audio-lingual discussions with experts, teachers, and students. A sequential explanatory design combines quantitative and qualitative methods for deeper understanding. Due to inconsistent official data, the researcher consulted the Federal Education Department and British Council. The population includes teachers, students, and exam content from SSC and O-Level schools. Stratified random sampling was used across Chiltan and Zarghoon towns. Quetta has 127 high schools, 761 SSC teachers, 80 O-Level teachers, 17,410 SSC students, and 1,600 O-Level students. The sample included 50 teachers, 5 students per school, and 20 experts from each system.

3.1 Research instrument

The questionnaire consisted of 50 questions, 26 questions and 26 questions along with 4 open-

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Section 1: Quantitative Findings

Table 4.1: The goals and objectives of the English language curriculum are aligned with: a) national requirements b) international requirements

		SDA	DA	N	A	SA	Total
Education System	SSC	9	11	24	72	34	150
	OLevel	2	1	7	34	6	50
Total		11	12	31	106	40	200
	Value		Df		Sig. (2-sided)		
Pearson Chi- Square	7.111 ^a		4		0.13		

The SDA, DA, N, A and SA representatives of Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree and Strongly Agree respectively.

Table 1: The estimated value of χ^2 exceeds the tabulated critical value at the 0.05 level according to the results obtained. Teachers at the SSC and O-level do not differ significantly in the frequency with which they express their support for SSC teachers, who fully agree with the statement that the goals and intentions of the English

ended questions from teachers, students, and experts from both frameworks. Instruments by Ajaz (2019), Kiyani (2002), Naeemullah (2007), and Umbreen (2008) provided direction. A semi-structured interview protocol of 5 open-ended questions was conducted with teachers, experts, and students. Study topics were addressed using a two-way focused group discussion methodology with teachers and experts. Data was collected through questionnaires to assess teachers' views on syllabus objectives and pattern of assessments. Teachers strengthened their perspectives through interview protocol with subject matter experts.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze data based on research objectives. Percentages and frequencies were found; hypothesis testing and the Chi-Square independence t -test were applied. Variables were categorical (nominal and ordinal), so the Pearson Chi-Square test was used. Data were processed using SPSS, and thematic analysis was used for qualitative analysis.

curriculum meet both national and international requirements. Therefore, the null hypothesis is true, so it can be said that the opinions of SSC teachers and O-level teachers on this premise are basically the same that goals and objectives of the English language curriculum are aligned with: a) national requirements b) international requirements.

Table 4.2: The present pattern of assessment comprises objectives that encompasses all domains of learning skills

		SDA	DA	N	A	SA	Total
Education System	SSC	6	6	40	54	44	150
	O Level	8	7	1	2	32	50
Total		14	13	41	56	76	200

Chi-Square Tests		Value	df	Sig.
Pearson Chi-Square		50.188a	4	0
Likelihood Ratio		57.753	4	0
Linear-by-Linear Association		0.029	1	0.866
N of Valid Cases		200		

The SDA, DA, N, A and SA representatives of Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree and Strongly Agree respectively

Table 2: The estimated value states that, in the SSC system, among 54 respondents agreeing, 6 indicated Strongly Disagree (SDA), 6 indicated Disagree (DA), 40 were Neutral (N), with the approach. In the O-level system, out of 200 respondents, 8 indicated SDA, 7 indicated DA, 1

was N, 2 agreed (A), and 32 strongly agreed (SA) with the approach. In four degrees of freedom, the estimated Pearson coefficient is 50.18 and the p-value is 0.000. the results suggested that there is significance difference exist between the O-level and SSC in present pattern of assessment comprises objectives that encompasses all domains of learning skills.

EXPERT'S DATA (SSC and O-LEVEL)

Table 4.3: The learning outcomes are clear and visible in English language curriculum.

		SDA	DA	N	A	SA	Total
Education System	SSC	1	3	2	12	2	20
	OLevel	1	0	0	14	5	20
	Total	2	3	2	26	7	40
		Value		Df		Asymp.	Sig. (2-sided)
	Pearson Chi-Square	6.440a		4		0.019	
	Likelihood Ratio	8.414		4		0.078	
	Linear-by-Linear Association	3.123		1		0.077	

The SDA, DA, N, A and SA representatives of Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree and Strongly Agree respectively

Table 3: It presents data on the visibility of learning outcomes in the English language curriculum across two educational systems SSC and O-level. The results states that the 12 experts of SSC are agreeing and 3 are disagreeing. The 19 experts of O-level Strongly Agreeing it means majority of the O-Level experts are agreeing. It

means the results from O-level majority are saying that the subject of English clearly defines the learning objectives. The results of Chi Square the significance value is 0.019 which is less than the 5% level of significance it means there is significance association exists between the SSC and O-level learning outcome are clear and visible in English language curriculum.

Table 4.4: The pattern of assessment can assess critically all learning domain.

		SDA	DA	N	A	SA	Total
Education System	SSC	8	2	0	8	2	20
	OLevel	0	3	2	6	9	20
	Total	8	5	2	14	11	40
		Value		Df		Asymp.	Sig. (2-sided)
	Pearson Chi-Square	14.940 ^a		4		0.005	
	Likelihood Ratio	19.169		4		0.001	
	Linear-by-Linear Association	7.953		1		0.005	

The SDA, DA, N, A and SA representatives of Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree and Strongly Agree respectively

Table 4: It depicts a comparison of perceptions

concerning whether the pattern of assessment can critically assess all learning domains within the context of English language education. Eight respondents expressed strong dissatisfaction, two

expressed dissatisfaction, no one took a neutral position, eight agreed, and two fully agreed with the SSC system. Regarding the O-level system, three respondents expressed their disagreement, two were neutral, six agreed, and nine strongly agreed. There are no respondents who would strongly disagree. With four degrees of freedom, Pearson's chi-squared test yielded a value of 14.940 and a p-value of

0.005. The statistical analysis suggests a significant difference in perceptions between the two education systems regarding the effectiveness of the assessment pattern in critically evaluating all learning domains within English language education. The p-value is below the conventional threshold of 0.05, indicating a meaningful distinction in opinions.

STUDENT'S DATA RESULTS (SSC and O-LEVEL)

Table 4.5: The goals and objectives of the English language curriculum are aligned with: (a) National requirements (b)International requirements

Education System	SDA	DA	Total
SSC	97	153	250
OLevel	9	41	50
Total	106	194	300
Chi-Square Tests	Value	Df	Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.890 ^a	1	0.005
Continuity Correction ^b	7.005	1	0.008
Likelihood Ratio	8.63	1	0.003
Linear-by-Linear Association	7.863	1	0.005

The SDA, DA, N, A and SA representatives of Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree and Strongly Agree respectively

Table 5: It states that there is a significant proportion (n= 97) strongly disagree with the alignment of English language curriculum goals and objectives with national and international requirements. Additionally, (n= 153) respondents disagree, contributing to a total of (n= 250) expressing some level of disagreement. Other hand, O-level education system, a much smaller number (n= 9) strongly disagree, and (n= 41) disagree, resulting in a total of 50 respondents expressing disagreement. The results of the chi-square tests suggest that there is a statistically significant association between the education

system (SSC or O-level) and the alignment of the goals and objectives of the English language curriculum with national and international requirements. A major correlation can be seen by the Chi-Square value of 7.890 with 1 degree of freedom and a p-value of 0.005. The theory of a significant relationship is supported by the likelihood ratio chi-square value of 8.63 with 1 degree of freedom and a p-value of 0.003.

The education system (SSC or O-level) and the English language curriculum's goals and aims' following national as well as international standards are shown to be significantly correlated, it may be determined.

Table 4.6: The present pattern of assessment broaden vision rather than working on grammar exercises.

	SDA	DA	N	A	SA	
SSC	48	86	28	81	7	250
OLevel	5	6	1	34	4	50
Total	53	92	29	115	11	300

The SDA, DA, N, A and SA representatives of Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree and Strongly Agree respectively

Table 6: It assessed the assessment patterns in English language learning, focusing on broadening vision rather than concentrating solely on grammar exercises. The findings

indicated a similar trend across both educational levels, with a notable emphasis on broadening vision over grammar exercises.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

Hypotesis-1

There is no significant difference between aims

and objectives in syllabus of English language of GCE (O-Level) and SSC level of education system.

Table 4.7: The goals and objectives of the English language curriculum are aligned with

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	S.E.Mean	SD	Sig.
National Requirements	96	53.3%				
International requirements	84	46.7%	1.66	0.12	1.62	0.37
Total	180	100%				

The SDA, DA, N, A and SA representatives of Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree and Strongly Agree respectively

The results states that there 53.3% respondents agreed on the statement that aims and objectives are aligned with national requirements where as 46.7 % agreed on international requirements. Referring to the table 4.1 of χ^2 at 5% level of significance with $df = 4$ is found that the tabulated $\chi^2 = 9.49$ and calculated value is 0.800, which describe that the calculated value is small

then the tabulated value. Thus null hypothesis is being accepted. Hence to conclude that the goals and objectives of the English language syllabus at the GCE (O-Level) and SSC system are not significantly different from one another.

Hypotesis-2

There is no significant difference between the assessment procedures of English language at GCE (O-Level) and SSC level of education system

Table 4.8: The pattern of assessment can assess critically all learning domain.

		SDA	DA	N	A	SA	Total
Education System	SSC	8	2	0	8	2	20
	OLevel	0	3	2	6	9	20
	Total	8	5	2	14	11	40
Chi-Square Tests	Value			Df		Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	
Pearson Chi-Square		14.940a		4		0.005	
Likelihood Ratio		19.169		4		0.001	
Linear-by-Linear Association		7.953		1		0.005	

The SDA, DA, N, A and SA representatives of Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree and Strongly Agree respectively

The results of table number 8 states that the SSC system the respondents strongly disagreed, 8 disagreed, 3 were neutral, 0 agreed, 8 and 2 strongly agreed. For the O-Level system, 0 respondents strongly disagreed, 3 disagreed, 2 was neutral, 6 agreed, and 9 strongly agreed. The Pearson Chi-Square test yielded a value of 14.90 with 4 degrees of freedom, resulting in a p-value of 0.005. The statistical analysis suggests that there is a marginally significant difference in perceptions between the two education systems the assessment procedures of English language at GCE (O-Level) and SSC level of education system.. The p-value is slightly above the conventional threshold of 0.005, indicating that there could be a trend towards significance. This difference might not be considered substantial enough to draw definitive

conclusions. The results cleared that the assessment procedures of English language at GCE (O-Level) and SSC system are not significantly different from one another.

4.2 SECTION II: qualitative analysis

In this section we have analysis qualitative analysis. Semi-structured interview protocol was employed. The semi-structured framework is the most prevalent interview style in qualitative research (DiCicco Bloom & Crabtree 2006), and interviews are the most widely adopted collecting information technique (Taylor 2005). Interview Protocol, 12 participants from both system including two experts, teachers and students from each system.

Focus Group Discussion, 10 participants from both system including two experts and three English language teachers from each system Focus groups discussion and interview protocols

were organized to discuss the research questions as part of the research.

1- What are the flaws in the current SSC English language syllabus in terms of aims and objectives?

2- In the O-Level and SSC system, what are the patterns of assessments?

Thematic Analysis

Theme1; Examining the SSC and O-Level English language syllabus

According to the majority of respondents, the SSC English language curriculum has not been updated for more than 18 years. The content of the curriculum is insufficient to provide an education that meet the needs of this challenging world and fails to make a live long learner. A curriculum that is confusing, insufficient, and poorly prepared hinders teachers and students from achieving the intended learning objectives. Most of the time, students use simple textbooks, like those from the Balochistan Education Board for grades 9th and 10th, which emphasises grammar exercises over other essential English language skills. Some respondents mentioned that SSC teachers strictly adhere to these textbooks. The responsibility for updating the curriculum lies with the curriculum department where as examining the English language syllabus of O-level system is up to date and frequently change after every two years and objectives of the English O-level curriculum helps student become more proficient in standard English by enhancing their understanding, significance, precision, and variety. It also assists student become innovative by utilizing language, experience, and creativity to develop unique ideas and have a positive influence on their life and education To develop; to develop critical thinking skills by improving their ability to identify, filter and analyze information; and to develop their ability to communicate effectively in English.

Sub-Theme; Syllabus comprises all communication skills in SSC system

The majority of respondents denied and stated that the current curriculum of English language provides a limited range of skills that do not meet the need of communication skills. Students never became autonomous learner or speaker. Teachers followed syllabus that only focused on writing and

reading skills and unfortunately students bounds inside their text books and cannot read or write outside of it. Some respondents stated that listening and speaking skills are far neglected by teachers and due to lack of language environment in institutions.

Sub-Theme; Students become autonomous learner

According to many interviewees, political and institutional constraints, such as the school district system, lack of basic methods to support teachers' autonomous learning, lack of students' ability to learn independently, and school rules and regulations are the main factors that hinder the development of students' autonomy in learning English. Respondants declared that to be autonomous, students must develop the skills necessary to learn difficult subjects on their own, with little help from teachers or trainers. For example, self-control, good time management, the ability to objectively self-assess, and the ability to set goals. However, our institutions do not provide students with an environment that fosters independence, and knowledge and skills do not automatically translate into independent learning. Students must be motivated and confident to use these skills and knowledge effectively. According to one group of veteran teachers, as learner discover more and more about the world, others and themselves, they become more curious and pursue things that satisfy them. To foster autonomy, learners must not only be able to develop a sense of control over their own learning (through practice and modeling), but they must also feel motivated and confident to participate successfully in the process (by offering rewards and constructive criticism). This should not be the case. Furthermore, this implies that autonomy depends on the learning situation. Learners may want to become autonomous individuals, but may not achieve this if the environment restricts their freedom of choice

Sub-Theme; Syllabus emphasizes students to think in target language in SSC system

According to most respondents, the English curriculum consists of comprehension lessons and grammar exercises, which means that teachers only create lesson plans. The sequence of sounds, words, phrases and/or grammatical structures that the teacher intends the students to acquire during

the lesson is known as target language. Because of the little space reserved for target language on lesson planning forms and the fact that target language is often only mentioned in the textbook along with chapter titles, it is easy to think of target language as a formal process. It just seems like a form to be filled out for accounting and copying purposes. However, the course focuses primarily on the target language.

Theme 4 Traditional pattern of assessment in SSC system

The majority of respondents declared that apart from the students, teachers also do not know what is being asked in exam paper. Assessment pattern is completely missing. Rote memorization and content knowledge are the only major aspect that are tested in exam paper. Students are not allowed to write on their own and even not given the opportunity to express their ideas, opinions, thoughts and messages in the exam paper. There is a dire need to change the pattern of assessment. Boards and examiners do not create new tasks to assess students' skills in all areas of English. They do not pay attention to uniform item placement (items that assess all skills) or task sequencing (tasks that cover all content areas), but focus only on understanding the subject matter to guide and assess learners. Other senior respondents declared that traditional system of assessment is implemented since time and students are used to for this type of pattern of assessing their knowledge and skills. In this way students as well as examiners do not want to leave their comfort zone.

Sub-Theme; Assessment of practical application of English language proficiency

Most respondents stated that in our SSC system, methods, including oral presentations, and some time group discussion, are employed to evaluate students' practical English language skills. We don't have a lot of time and guideline to make the students do exercises other than book exercises. Some of these activities focus on topics related to their coursework. In the O-level system, majority of respondents stated that they employ diverse assessment methods to evaluate student's practical English language skills, like oral assessments, role-play, presentations on topics, debates on contemporary issues, class discussions, interviews and dialogues. This enables us assess

their ability to communicate fluently and effectively in real-life situation. Apart from oral presentations we incorporate project-based learning activities where students collaborate to research plan and present findings in English. Additionally, written assignments are used to evaluate their written communication skills.

Sub-Theme; Proper assessment of developed skills
 The assessment of Basic English language skills is a top priority for SSC teachers and evaluators. They emphasize contextual relevance and practical application, as well as continuous feedback for improvement. On the other hand, O-level teachers and practitioners focus on advanced competency assessment and emphasize global benchmarks, outcome-based assessment, and the application of valid and reliable strategies to prepare students for vocational and higher education.

ANALYSIS OF INTERVIEW RESPONSES

Interviews were conducted with subject matter experts, teachers, and students from key institutions of both education systems in Quetta city. Their thoughts and suggestions are summarized below. The appendix contains detailed responses to the questions.

RESPONSES FROM TEACHERS (SSC and O-LEVEL)

1- What are the aims and objectives of the English programme in each system?

The syllabus of English language teaching at SSC is designed to achieve general educational objectives. However, specific details may vary depending on regional conditions and local educational interests. In general, the program includes language skills, cultural sensitivity, analytical and critical thinking, test-taking strategies, functional communication, reading comprehension, and written expression. The SSC English language curriculum aims to inculcate the language and communication skills into students that are necessary to function successfully in the modern world, taking into account the specific characteristics of each district to achieve these goals.

2- WHAT ARE YOUR VIEWS ON THE ASSESSMENT PATTERN APPLIED TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AT THE SSC LEVEL?

The assessment model usually consists of a combination of written tests, oral exams and practical work to comprehensively assess students' language skills. However, great emphasis should be placed on learner-centered teaching strategies that enable learners to actively participate in their own learning.

RESPONSES FROM EXPERTS (SSC AND O-LEVEL)

3- What are the strength and weaknesses of the current English language curriculum in the education system of both streams?

The O-level curriculum aims to develop the skills necessary for learners to become independent learners and speakers of English, in addition to the abilities essential to ensure that every student advantages from learning English,

The SSC's English curriculum has not been updated for more than 10 years. The curriculum does not meet the requirements for quality education. An uncertain, inaccurate, and inadequate curriculum will not help teachers and students achieve the desired learning outcomes.

4 WHAT CHANGES SHOULD BE MADE IN THE PATTERN OF ASSESSMENT IN BOTH STREAMS?

A combination of formative and summative assessment is effective in SSC's English assessment system. This includes continuous language assessment, frequent written assignments, and interactive tests to determine the extent of language use in real-life situations. Furthermore, a balanced combination of objective and subjective assessment methods provides a comprehensive view of a learner's language proficiency. Practical language skills and critical analysis of literature can be used to create a more comprehensible model for the O-level system English exam. In order to better assess understanding of linguistic nuances, subjective assessment could be introduced and not rely on purely objective judgments.

RESPONSES FROM STUDENTS (SSC and O-LEVEL)

5- What measures should be taken to improve pattern of assessment?

The students realized that the exam should focus on practical skills rather than purely theoretical knowledge. In addition to a variety of decision-

making questions, we want more opportunities to demonstrate our written and oral skills. Instead of testing our ability to understand the language, current exams often test our ability to memorize. We need tests that encourage creative thinking and sound reasoning. Assessment design should be more flexible. For example, instead of a single final exam, ongoing assessment can take the form of work plans, presentations and group discussions, and the assessment should be more responsive to real-life conditions. Our ability to communicate effectively in English should be assessed, not just our knowledge of punctuation.

DICUSSION

1- English Language Curriculum Have Well Defined and Clear Aims and Objectives for (GCE O-LEVEL/ SSC)

Several significant conclusions are drawn from the study, which contrasts the opinions of SSC and O-level teachers on various facets of the English language curriculum:

The relationship between the objectives of the curriculum with national and international standards: Statistical analyses have shown that there was no statistically significant difference in the assessments between teachers at the SSC level and O-level regarding the alignment of the curriculum objectives with national as well as international standards (table 1, 3) . Although instructors at the SSC and O-levels generally agreed on the readability and importance of the learning objectives, the statistical analysis rejected the null hypothesis. Data with a likelihood value of fewer or less than 5% shows a significant difference of clarity between the two systems.

Pattern of Assessment Critically Assess and Emphasize Practical Skills and Opportunities for Written and Oral Communication in GCE (O-Level) and SSC System

They stressed the importance of assessing effective communication in English, not just grammar. According to the respondents, the content of the assessment is not clear to either students or teachers. Current assessment focuses on memorization and content knowledge, which limits students' ability to express themselves (table 8). As traditional methods resist change, there is a strong push to reform assessment methods. Negative attitudes towards the education system will be fostered by outdated

methods. Practical skills in English are assessed by a variety of methods, including oral presentations and group discussions, in addition to essay-type questions in examinations. Teachers at O-level use strategies such as role-play and discussion to assess communication in real-life situations. While O-level teachers focus on advanced skills and global standards, SSC level teachers emphasize (table 2). Formative and summative evaluations complement each other effectively in SSC's English assessment method.

CONCLUSION

The study focused on a comparative analysis of English language programs in the GCE O-Level and SSC systems to identify the strengths and weaknesses of English language curriculum and assessment patterns. The actual outcome that was included as an objectives and aims in the English language curriculum at SSC Level will not be adequate to meet the future needs of Pakistan .It promotes memorization of paragraphs and other writing skills while the O-level curriculum develops and promotes artistic writing. In order to improve the conceptual development and understanding of students at SSC level, changes need to be made in the assessment pattern. O-level assessment, which emphasizes more on conceptual understanding and encourages creativity, is considered to much better in this regard compared to SSC level assessment, which emphasizes more on memorization. Both systems agree that formative assessment is essential to measure pupils' progress on an ongoing basis, and the examinations cover the whole of the intended subject of English.

REFERENCES

Ajaz Shaheen, (2017). General certificate education (A-Level) and higher secondary certificate education system with special reference to physics: A comparative study. PhD Thesis submitted to Hamdard Institute of Education and Social Sciences, Hamdar University.

Ahmad, H., & Shah, S. R. (2014). EFL TEXTBOOKS: EXPLORING THE SUITABILITY OF TEXTBOOK CONTENTS FROM EFL

TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVE. VFAST Transactions on Education and Social Sciences, 2(1), 87-95.

Akram, M., & Mahmood, A. (2007). The status and teaching of English in Pakistan. *Language in India*, 7(12), 1-7.

Al-Arifi, R. S. (2020). Difficulties facing teaching English language at the primary level from the point of view of teachers and the proposed solutions for them in Al-Quwaiyah Governorate. *Reading and Knowledge Journal*, 20(2), 117-148.

Bhatti, M. S., & Mukhtar, R. (2017). Analyzing the utility of grammar translation method & direct method for teaching English at intermediate level. *IJAEDU-International E-Journal of Advances in Education*, 3(7), 60-67

Baloch, A. H., Baloch, G. H., & Faiz, J. (2022). Proto-historic Balochistan: Evidence from Mehrgarh. *Pakistan Languages and Humanities Review*, 6(3), 826-839

Brown, J. D., & Rodgers, T. S. (2002). *Doing second language research: An introduction to the theory and practice of second language research for graduate/master's students in TESOL and applied linguistics, and others*. Oxford university press.

DiCicco-Bloom B. & Crabtree B. F. (2006) The qualitative research interview. *Medical Education*, 40(4), 314-321. DOI:10.1111/j.1365-2929.2006.02418.x

Fareed, M., Bilal, M., & Saeed, N. (2016). Impact Of Global Variation On English Language In Pakistan: Perceptions Of Pakistani English Language Teachers. *Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 4(2), 26.

Hasan, R., Matthiessen, C. M., & Webster, J. J. (Eds.). (2005). *Continuing Discourse on Language: A Functional Perspective*, Volumes 1 and 2. University of Toronto Press.

Kearsley, G and Lynch, W., 1996, 'Structural issues in distance education', *Journal of Education for Business*, 71(4), pp. 191-6.

Kayani, M. (2002). *A comparative Study of Secondary and GCE O level Science.Education Programme in Pakistan*. (Unpublished) Ph.D Thesis, University of Arid Agriculture Rawalpindi, Pakistan.

Muhammad Iqbal Naem (2011). *A comparative*

- study of secondary school certificate (SSC) and general certificate of education-ordinary level (GCE O-Level) English language course. PhD Dissertation submitted to Department of Faculty of Social Sciences, International Islamic University Education, Islamabad, Pakistan.
- Mahboob, A. (2009). English as an Islamic language: A case study of Pakistani English. *World Englishes*, 28(2), 175-189.
- Malik, G.B. & Anwar, M. (2011). Comparative analyses of the teaching methods and evaluation practices in English subject at secondary school certificate (SSC) and general certificate of education (GCE O-Level) in Pakistan. *International Education Studies*, 4(1), 202-211.
- Muhammad, S. (2011). L2 reading instruction and reading beliefs of English teachers in public sector universities in Pakistan (Unpublished M.A. Thesis). Northern Arizona University, Flagstaff, USA.
- Naeemullah, M. (2007). Comparative study of curricula, teaching methodology and examination system of GCE (A-level) and F.Sc level in Basic Sciences. (Unpublished) Ph.D Thesis University of Arid Agricultural Rawalpindi Pakistan).
- Shamim, F. (2008) Trends, Issues and Challenges in English Language Education in Pakistan. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*. Taylor M. C. (2005) Interviewing. In *Qualitative Research in Health Care*. (Holloway I. ed.), McGraw-Hill Education, Maidenhead, England, p. 39-55.
- The British Council. (2012). Cambridge registered GCE School in Pakistan. Retrieved from: www.british.council.org/pk-exams-cic-centres-list-pdf
- Umbreen, I. (2008). A Study on social acceptability of “O” and “A” levels of education system and its implications in Pakistan.(Ph.D. Dissertation, Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan).

